

Dynamic Predictive Quantization for Staggered SAR Systems: Algorithm Description and Experiments with Real SAR Data

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OBPDC 2022

Knowledge for Tomorrow

Outline

- Introduction and application scenario of staggered SAR
- Dynamic Predictive Block-Adaptive Quantization (DP-BAQ)
- Performance Analysis on Airborne F-SAR Data
- Conclusions and Outlook

Future SAR Systems: staggered SAR acquisition principle

Wide Swath with **constant** PRI

Wide Swath with **staggered** PRI

M. Villano, G. Krieger, A. Moreira. "Staggered SAR: High-resolution wide-swath imaging by continuous PRI variation" TGRS 2013.

Increase of onboard data

Downlink bottleneck

Reduce onboard data

Low complexity

Tandem-L – A Proposal for the First Staggered SAR Mission

- DLR proposal for bistatic, fully polarimetric L-band InSAR mission
- Main goal: monitoring of dynamic Earth processes
- Four “spheres” of applications: **bio**-, **geo**-, **idro**-, and **cryo**-sphere
- Large swath width achieved with digital beamforming (DBF) in elevation

	Resolution	Swath
TerraSAR-X	$\sim 3\text{ m}$	$\sim 30\text{ km}$
Tandem-L	$< 10\text{ m}$	$\sim 350\text{ km}$

Reduce onboard data

Low Complexity

Raw data quantized at
4bps \rightarrow 16 TB/day

Up to **50%** of data volume reduction with
significant computational burden
(~ 15 range lines to be stored onboard)

M. Villano et. Al., Onboard processing for data volume reduction in high-resolution wide-swath SAR, IEEE TGRS, 2016

Oversampling in Staggered SAR – Opportunity for Data Volume Reduction

- **Oversampling osf** is introduced in azimuth to allow efficient **reconstruction** of the missing information (data gaps) through BLU interpolation

$$osf = \frac{PRF}{PBW} \sim 140\%$$

Parameter	Value
Band	L ($\lambda=23.8$ cm)
System	Staggered SAR
Antenna	Equiv. to ~ 10 m planar
Mean PRF	2700 Hz
Doppler PBW	1130 Hz

- Certain autocorrelation ρ in the data introduced by the antenna pattern weighting (usually negligible for conventional SAR)

Data Volume Reduction: Exploiting LPC and BAQ

- Linear Predictive Coding (LPC) exploits existing redundancy to achieve **reduction of the data volume**

$$d[n] = x[n] - \tilde{x}[n]$$

$$\tilde{x}[n] = \sum_{i=1}^N \beta_i x[n - i]$$

- Block Adaptive Quantization (BAQ) adapts the quantization parameters to the **local statistics** of a considered block in range.

Dynamic Predictive Block-Adaptive Quantization (DP-BAQ)

Evaluation of DP-BAQ on Synthetic SAR Raw Data

$$SQNR = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^I |x_i|^2}{\sum_{i=1}^I |q_i|^2}$$

25% data reduction

Martone, M., Gollin, N., Villano, M., Rizzoli, P., & Krieger, G. **Predictive Quantization for Data Volume Reduction in Staggered SAR Systems.** TGRS 2020

DLR F-SAR Airborne Radar

- DLR experimental airborne SAR
- Full modular system in X-, C-, S-, **L-** and P-bands
- Full Polarimetric capability
- Single-pass polarimetric interferometry capability in X- and S-bands
- Four recording channels with data rates of up to 2 Gbit/s per unit.
- Precise internal calibration (relative accuracy better than 1 dB).
- Fully reconfigurable operation modes including capability for digital beamforming on receive.
- Repeat-pass Pol-InSAR as standard measurement mode for ensuring baseline flexibility.

R. Horn *et al.*, "F-SAR — DLR's new multifrequency polarimetric airborne SAR" IGARSS 2009.

Experimental F-SAR Data

- L-band acquisition over Kaufbeuren (Bavaria) of about 8km x 3 km [az x rg]

Parameter	Value
PRF	2500 Hz
δ_{rg}	0.4 m
δ_{az}	0.6 m
osf	19

From F-SAR to Tandem-L: Raw Data Emulation

- Data provided in **Range-Compressed** format
- **Low-Pass filtering** to avoid aliasing
- **Downsampling** to reproduce the target azimuth autocorrelation (ρ_1)
- **Non-Uniform resampling** & insertion of blind ranges (**gaps**) according to Tandem-L-like staggered PRI sequence
- **Quantization** with $N_b = [2, 3, 4, 6]$ bps for BAQ and DP-BAQ with prediction order $N = [1 \dots 4]$
- **BLU interpolation** & **SAR Focusing**
- **Performance evaluation** on the final SAR image

Performance Evaluation: SQNR & Phase Errors

Performance Evaluation: 2D SQNR

$$\Delta_{\text{SQNR}, \sigma_i^0} = E \left[\text{SQNR}_{\text{BAQ}, \sigma_i^0}^{4 \text{ bps}} - \text{SQNR}_{\text{DP-BAQ}, \sigma_i^0}^{3 \text{ bps}} \right]$$

Performance Analysis: NESZ

- **Noise equivalent sigma zero** represents the system noise floor.
A way to estimate it from data is to exploit specular reflection over calm water bodies

$$\text{NESZ} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=k}^{k+N} \sigma^0[i] \quad \text{Average along azimuth}$$

Conclusions and Outlook

- Staggered SAR for HRWS & Tandem-L
- DP-BAQ for onboard data reduction evaluated on simulated and F-SAR airborne data
- Consistent data volume reduction (20-25%) achieved and low onboard computational effort (only 4 range lines to be stored)

Outlook

- Backscatter-dependent analysis: performance & bit rate allocation optimized exploiting apriori backscatter information
- Implementation of more elaborated predictors (e.g., non-causal LPC)

